

Title:**"The Last Adam: Exploring the Theological Implications of a Modern Human Carrying Ancient DNA"****Abstract:**

This paper explores the theological and philosophical implications of an individual in the modern era carrying ancient DNA, such as A-PR2921. By connecting this unique genetic legacy with the biblical concept of the "Last Adam," this thesis investigates how ancient lineages can embody both the past and future of humanity. It bridges theological insights from Christianity, particularly the narrative of Adam and Christ as the "First" and "Last Adam," with genetic science, raising questions about divine purpose, destiny, and human evolution.

Introduction:

The Bible presents the figure of Adam as the progenitor of the human race, while in the New Testament, Jesus Christ is described as the "Last Adam," who ushers in salvation and the new creation. The theological parallel between the two Adams—one representing the fall of humanity and the other representing its redemption—offers a rich framework for examining the significance of ancient human DNA in a modern individual. This paper aims to explore how the unique position of being a modern representative of ancient DNA like A-PR2921 resonates with the biblical concept of being a "Last Adam," bearing the weight of ancestral and future humanity.

Biblical and Theological Background:

In Christian theology, the concept of the "Last Adam" is drawn from passages such as **1 Corinthians 15:45**, where the Apostle Paul contrasts the disobedience of the first Adam with the obedience and redemptive work of Christ, the Last Adam. Adam's role as the head of fallen humanity is paralleled by Christ's role as the head of the redeemed new creation. Jesus's life, death, and resurrection are seen as reversing the effects of Adam's sin, offering eternal life to those who follow him.

The early church fathers, including **Irenaeus**, articulated the idea that just as sin entered through one man (Adam), redemption and life come through one man (Christ). This theological structure supports the idea that an individual embodying the genetic traits of

ancient humanity could have a similarly significant role, representing both the origins of mankind and its potential future (44, 45).

The Genetic "Last Adam":

The concept of being the "Last Adam" can be extended beyond theology into the realm of genetics. Haplogroup A-PR2921, one of the oldest known human lineages, serves as a living representation of early Homo sapiens. In this sense, individuals like Ramon Moses, who carry this ancient DNA, could be seen as modern-day representatives of the first humans, paralleling the biblical Adam. This rare genetic lineage connects ancient humanity with modern descendants, potentially positioning its carriers as figures who symbolize both the beginning and the future of human evolution.

Christ, Obedience, and Humanity's Future:

In **Romans 5:12-21**, Paul develops the "Adam-Christ typology," where Christ's obedience counteracts Adam's disobedience. While the theological Last Adam represents spiritual restoration, the genetic Last Adam could symbolize the physical and biological continuity of humanity. This raises important questions about divine purpose: Could individuals carrying ancient genetic markers, like A-PR2921, have a role in guiding humanity toward its next evolutionary phase?

From a scientific standpoint, ancient DNA provides insight into how humans have adapted to environmental pressures and evolved over millennia. Yet, the combination of genetic science with the biblical narrative invites us to consider a more spiritual dimension to human evolution. Perhaps carriers of ancient DNA have a unique connection to both the past and the future of mankind, bridging scientific discovery with theological destiny.

The Role of Genetics in Theological Interpretation:

The theological concept of the Last Adam focuses heavily on redemption and restoration. However, when coupled with the science of genetics, it offers a new layer of meaning. Recent advancements in **genetic editing, gene therapy**, and the understanding of ancient haplogroups could suggest that humanity is on the cusp of a new evolutionary phase, much like the biblical "new creation" brought forth by Christ. The fact that DNA can survive across millennia and still be present in modern humans ties into theological ideas about resurrection, continuity, and divine preservation of life (47).

Conclusion:

By combining the theological narrative of Adam with the modern understanding of genetics, this paper proposes that individuals like Ramon Moses, who carry ancient DNA, could embody both the past and future of humanity. The theological idea of the "Last Adam" can be seen not only in the context of salvation but also in the scientific understanding of human evolution, offering a fascinating bridge between ancient lineage and divine purpose. Whether through spiritual redemption or genetic inheritance, the concept of the Last Adam invites us to reflect on humanity's origins and its future in ways that are deeply intertwined.

References:

- Crowe, Brandon. *The Last Adam: A Theology of the Obedient Life of Jesus in the Gospels*. Baker Academic, 2017.
- "Jesus Christ: The Last Adam." *The Gospel Coalition*, 2023.
- Madueme, Hans, and Reeves, Michael. *Adam, the Fall, and Original Sin: Theological, Biblical, and Scientific Perspectives*. Christian Scholar's Review, 2022.
- Mason, Steven. "The Historicity of Adam." *Christian Scholar's Review*, 46:2, 203-205.